

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

Call: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02

Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

D6.1: Meetings Reports (First Period)

Lead partner: APRE

Authors: Riccardo Coletta, APRE
Flaminia Rocca, APRE

Reviewer: Paola Zerilli, UoY

Submission date: 31/10/2023

Dissemination level		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), or the UKRI. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained herein.

Document history

Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
12/10/2023	1.0	1 st draft by APRE
25/10/2023	1.1	Review by UoY
27/10/2023	1.2	Final version by APRE

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS 3

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY..... 4

1 PROJECT OVERVIEW..... 5

2 INTRODUCTION 6

3 MEETINGS REPORTS (M1 – M12) 7

3.1 KICK-OFF MEETING (NOVEMBER 2022)..... 7

3.2 1ST MONTHLY MEETING (DECEMBER 2022)11

3.3 2ND MONTHLY MEETING (JANUARY 2023)14

3.4 3RD MONTHLY MEETING (FEBRUARY 2023)16

3.5 4TH MONTHLY MEETING & CONSORTIUM GENERAL ASSEMBLY (MARCH 2023).....19

3.6 5TH MONTHLY MEETING (APRIL 2023)21

3.7 6TH MONTHLY MEETING (MAY 2023)23

3.8 7TH MONTHLY MEETING (JUNE 2023)25

3.9 8TH MONTHLY MEETING (JULY 2023)27

3.10 9TH MONTHLY MEETING (AUGUST 2023)29

3.11 10TH MONTHLY MEETING (OCTOBER 2023).....30

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current document, titled “MARINEWIND Meetings Reports (First Period)”, contains all the information related to the meetings organised by APRE, as Project Coordinator, during the first 12 months of the project, including the kick-off meeting, held in November 2022, and the General Assembly, held in March 2023 to discuss the termination of the UK Associated Partner Element Energy Ltd (ELE). The present deliverable, linked to Task 6.1 - Project Management, was developed by APRE and reviewed, as per the Quality Management Plan, by the Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Paola Zerilli of UoY.

1 PROJECT OVERVIEW

MARINEWIND is a 36-month Coordination and Support Action that will identify bottlenecks and potential opportunities to strengthen **Floating Offshore Wind Technology (FOWT)** role in delivering innovative solutions to system integration and will consider how best to integrate such a system by exploring the market, policy and regulations issues, social, financial, and techno-economic optimal solutions, and provision for storage and flexibility recommendations.

The MARINEWIND methodology is based on the analysis of the MARINEWIND Labs, which are social, environmental, technological, and financial pilot studies based upon a multi-faceted data collection and analysis on barriers and enablers related to:

- a) policy measures (**WP1**),
- b) societal engagement and environmental impact (**WP2**),
- c) financial solutions, techno-economic implications, and commercialisation of FOWTs (**WP3**).

The **MARINEWIND Labs** are in five countries: **Portugal and UK (actual applications of FOWTs) and Greece, Spain, and Italy (planned applications of FOWTs)**. These Labs will support the transfer of knowledge from the established experiences to the potential FOWT sites where plans for installation of FOWTs are still at various stages of planning or implementation.

The MARINEWIND Labs will involve the **Quintuple Helix stakeholders (industry, academia, public authorities, civil society, and green innovation)**. The threefold analysis will be conveyed into the **MARINEWIND web based Geographical Information System (WebGIS)** which will provide specifically tailored information on FOWT to the various stakeholders based on their category, geographical location and their goals and policy recommendations on how to have more informed RES policies and how to increase societal acceptance (**WP4**).

The Replicability Plan will support the transfer of knowledge. **Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities (WP5)** will ensure widespread outreach of the project results and outcomes and to reach its impacts.

2 INTRODUCTION

In order to best fulfil the contractual obligations of the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA), APRE, as Project Coordinator, managed the activities by monitoring the progress of the project on a monthly basis, as indicated by D6.6 - Project Management Plan.

During the monthly meetings, the consortium was asked to provide a report on:

- day-to-day internal administrative management;
- work progress, including quality assurance and timely delivery of project results (deliverables, milestones, reports, events, etc.);
- financial status;
- refinement and updating of the work plan, if necessary, including verification of critical risks for implementation and mitigation measures;
- any communications to be addressed to other members of the Consortium or to the Project Officer (EC);
- organisation and development of events and other communication and dissemination activities.

The first meeting, i.e. the kick-off meeting, was organised by APRE at M1 (14th and 15th November, 2022), in order to build a work team for effective and smooth project implementation. The other monthly meetings of the first period (M2 - M12) were held in virtual mode, via the Teams platform.

Furthermore, a MARINEWIND Consortium General Assembly was held in March 2023, in order to discuss and approve the termination of the UK Associated Partner Element Energy Ltd (ELE).

Since MARINEWIND consortium is quite small and therefore the internal communication was continuous for the entire twelve months (e.g., through e-mails), the monthly meetings were quite short (generally lasting from one to two hours maximum) and served mainly to recap the progress of the activities, given that the individual issues were analysed and resolved separately.

In fact, in addition to the monthly meetings, whenever needed, APRE organised separate *ad hoc* (bilateral and/or thematic) meetings, relating to the technical aspects of the project, or to further management issues, with the various WPs and Task leaders, to discuss the development of individual activities, operational difficulties and critical issues that did not require the attention of the entire consortium.

Below is a summary table of the various meetings.

Type	Date	Venue
Kick-off Meeting	2022/11/14 & 15	Rome & Civitavecchia, Italy
1 st Monthly Meeting	2022/12/13	Teams Platform
2 nd Monthly Meeting	2023/01/10	Teams Platform
3 rd Monthly Meeting	2023/02/14	Teams Platform
4 th Monthly Meeting & General Assembly	2023/03/14	Teams Platform

5 th Monthly Meeting	2023/04/11	Teams Platform
6 th Monthly Meeting	2023/05/16	Teams Platform
7 th Monthly Meeting	2023/06/15	Teams Platform
8 th Monthly Meeting	2023/07/11	Teams Platform
9 th Monthly Meeting	2023/08/29	Teams Platform
10 th Monthly Meeting	2023/10/10	Teams Platform

3 MEETINGS REPORTS (M1 – M12)

3.1 KICK-OFF MEETING (November 2022)

Kick – Off Meeting
MARINEWIND - Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)
14-15/11/2022

PARTICIPANTS LIST		
Name Surname	Organisation	On site / Remote
Riccardo Coletta	APRE	On site
Arianna D'Addezio	APRE	On site
Silvia Troiteiro	SENER	On site
Leonidas Parodos	Q-PLAN	On site
Georgios Spyridopoulos	Q-PLAN	On site
Janete Gonçalves	WAVEC	On site
Luca Greco	CNR	On site
Stefano Maran	RSE	On site
Francesco Lanni	RSE	On site
Giuseppe Palazzo	RSE	On site
Laura Serri	RSE	On site
Davide Airoidi	RSE	On site
Paola Zerilli	UoY	On site
Eveline Sleiman	ESC	On site
Inés Tunga	ESC	On site
Baris Adiloglu	Project Officer (CINEA)	Remote
Gianinoni Iva Maria	RSE	Remote
Alessia Lucarelli	CNR	Remote

The first day of the Kick Off Meeting (14/11/2022) was held in APRE headquarter in Rome. The day started with the welcome and greetings of Riccardo Coletta from APRE (project coordinator (PC)). Riccardo, together with Paola Zerilli, from University of York, scientific coordinator of MARINEWIND, have presented the main objectives and the outcomes of the project. The technical and organizational aspects of the project have been addressed too.

Every participants then introduced themselves, one by one, to the project officer (PO), Mr. Baris Adiloglu (remote participation), and all the partners explained their organization / entity that is directly involved within the project.

The PO spoke during the first part of the meeting highlighting, in particular, the main expectations of the European Commission in relation to the MARINEWIND project. All the project management aspects have been discussed with a focus on 1) the **communication between the PC and PO** and on 2) the **timeline of the project**, with the aim to identify the entire timeline of MARINEWIND.

Following, each of the work package leader (WPL) presented the work package (WP) with the aim to present all the activities and to start a working collaboration with all the task leaders.

Following, the discussion points for each of the WP:

1) WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation

RSE, as WPL, has been supported during the presentation of WP1 by the task leaders (APRE, ESC and CNR).

All the activities have been presented, in particular:

- Analysis of policy and regulatory barriers and enablers to floating offshore wind deployment;
- The development of a stakeholders database;
- Elaboration of results of policy analysis.

Discussion points: It has been noted how the duration of T.1.3 could be adapted in relation to the MARINEWIND activities.

2) WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis

SENER, as WPL, has been supported during the presentation of WP2 by the respective task leader (RSE and CNR). All the activities have been presented, in particular:

- Analysis of social and environmental barriers and enablers;
- Elaboration of the results and environmental analysis.

For each of the Task and Subtask, Silvia Troiteiro (from SENER) underlined the main inputs needed for the implementation of the specific activities as well as the main outputs.

Discussion points: the main points discussed during the WP2 presentation are:

- 1) *The duration and the interaction of the Task 1.3. (Labs co-creation activities), Task 3.3. (MARINEWIND surveys), Task 2.1 (Analysis of social and environmental barriers and enablers).*

In particular, it was noted how could be necessary to postpone / anticipate the tasks to ensure and achieve the MARINEWIND objectives;

- 2) *Move Task 2.1 beginning from M1 to M4 to cover lab in M20 or extend Task 2.1 minimum to M21 without increasing dedication and;*
- 3) *Lab M10 is in August' 23 and it is proposed to move it to M11 or M12 (September or October'23 as well as Lab M15 is in January' 24 to move it to M16 (February'24).*

3) WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey

Paola Zerilli (UoY) presented the WP3 on the financing, techno-economic analysis that will be crucial for the implementation of MARINEWIND activities. All the task and subtask have been presented with the goal to define all the activities for improving knowledge and awareness of financial barriers and enablers and financial market incentives for FOWT; for improving technological awareness of market players to help them understanding how to and when to enter the market and for facilitating the access to green finance and fostering the market uptake of the innovative FOWT solutions analyzed within the MARINEWIND Labs.

Discussion points: no discussion points have been addressed within this WP.

4) WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools

Q-PLAN presented the WP4 supported by the task leaders (RSE, Q-PLAN and APRE). All the activities have been presented with the goal to 1) discuss on the development of MARINEWIND webGIS tool; 2) to put the basis for the definition of recommendations for MARINEWIND stakeholders; and 3) to define the topics of the webinars for policy makers and public authorities. The MARINEWIND Replicability Plan has been discussed too.

Discussion points: the main points discussed are:

- *The webGIS use and the platform that will be utilized;*
- *How to access information across the Web services;*
- *One point that has been underlined is that could be a problem on sharing the geographical information and on this it would be necessary to think what could be the information that can be geographical linked;*
- *Deliverables timetable (most the deliverables have the same deadline - M36).*

5) WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Janete Gonçalves from WAVEC, as WP5 leader, presented the WP on dissemination, communication and exploitation supported by the task leaders, APRE and Q-PLAN. The goal of the WP5 presentation was to put the basis of the communication plan (that will be crucial for a long term dissemination of the project and to maximize MARINEWIND results and outcomes) and to define even the MARINEWIND visual identity. On this, the WPL presented the logo of the project as well as the PowerPoint template, even if it has been already shared, to be used for the KoM, with the entire consortium before the KoM.

Discussion points: the discussion points tackled during the WP5 presentation are the following:

- *To consider, as starting point, platform already in place at local and international level with the goal to strengthen the exchange of best practices (e.g., RES platform already in place and WINDEUROPE platform).*

6) WP6: Project Management

The PC described the project management, underling that UoY will be the scientific coordinator of the project. The PC deepened the following issues:

- Meetings organization (included the virtual and the monthly ones);
- He presented the MARINEWIND SharePoint as working space and depository one;
- Report periods;
- Budget;
- MARINEWIND Advisory Board;
- Data Management Plan and ethics;
- WP6 Deliverables.

Discussion points:

- *Participation during the monthly meeting of both, WPL and TL and schedule of the monthly meeting;*
- *Possibility to add other participants in the MARINEWIND Advisory Board.*

The second day of the KoM (15/11/2022) has been organized in Civitavecchia with the goal to have an on-the-ground experience and to have a direct confrontation with the local authorities who are working on green and sustainable technological transformations, with a focus on harbor renewal.

In the morning, the MARINEWIND consortium participated to the presentation of the Green Transition Plan for Civitavecchia city held at the headquarter of the Port Authority in Civitavecchia.

The plan has been presented by the Councilor for Ecological Transition and Digital Transformation, Roberta Lombardi, supported by Mr. Pino Musolino, harbor authority.

Roberta Lombardi underlined how one of the main aspect for the development of the plan has been the community engagement that participated, with a pro-active approach, from the beginning of its evolution, allowing the development of a plan based on the real needs of the entire community.

The bottom-up engagement approach has demonstrated how important is to respect and actively involve all the parts of the society, trying to respond to the different needs, leaving nobody behind.

Furthermore, she underlined how Civitavecchia houses a coal-fired power station and the Green Transition plan foresees its overcome with the conversion of energy and production based on renewable sources, with the aim to develop a '*renewable energy district of Lazio region*'. The latter could become an area of strategic interest based on a strong interaction between the harbors and the internal areas, and could increase the investments attraction as well as the competitiveness between the local companies and creating new employment opportunities linked to the Blue-economy and to the eco-innovation.

Professor Livio de Santoli and Professor Franco Rispoli have spoken too during the day; both have underlined how important is to develop and to use, within the national context, sustainable resources as the hydrogen (underlined by Professor de Santoli) and the wind, through the development of wind offshore park (underlined by Professor Rispoli).

The latter focused on the importance of the wind offshore solutions, emphasizing how it could be a feasible answer to the climate change and to the rising energy prices. Finally, he also addressed crucial issues, as the engagement of fisheries sector and bird associations. This issue was also addressed by Paola during the first day of the KoM and she underlined the importance to have, within the MARINEWIND consortium, a fisheries association with the goal to listen their real needs and try to answer to them.

Lastly, Sapienza Innovazione focuses the speech on the detailed presentation of the Plan presenting the KPIs that have been inserted within the plan.

During the second part of the day, instead, the consortium together with the Councilor Lombardi, the harbor authorities and engineers, have visited the Civitavecchia harbor site. The visit interested all the harbor parts that are affected by energy and re-development works.

The consortium participation to the presentation of the plan and the visit to the harbor sites represent a potential collaboration and it is a first step for MARINEWIND to develop new synergies, encouraging the exchange of best practices between European areas engaged in ecological transition paths with a particular attention to the energy sector renewable.

3.2 1st MONTHLY MEETING (December 2022)

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2022-12-13

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta; Arianna D'Addezio

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

Name	Initials	Organization
Riccardo Coletta	RC	APRE
Arianna D'Addezio	ADA	APRE
Raquel Juan Hernandez	RJH	SENER
Leonidas Parodos	LP	Q-PLAN
Georgios Spyridopoulos	GS	Q-PLAN
Ana Brito e Melo	ABM	WAVEC
Elena Ciappi	EC	CNR
Luca Greco	LG	CNR
Francesco Lanni	FL	RSE
Giuseppe Palazzo	GP	RSE
Laura Serri	LS	RSE
Davide Airoidi	DA	RSE
Rosalie Tukker	RT	EUROPECHE
Paola Zerilli	PZ	UoY
Connor Innes	CI	ESC
Inés Tunga	IT	ESC

MINUTES

The first monthly meeting was held on December 14, 2022, remotely (length: 1 hour). The meeting addressed the various WPs with a focus on the actions foreseen for the first semester. Below the main points addressed for each WP:

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation

Davide from RSE (as WPL) said that he started collecting papers and various documents from the stakeholders, with the aim of starting the analysis and understanding the market design. To better coordinate the internal work, Elena (CNR) suggested organizing various meetings, one for each WP, starting from next week.

Moreover, on this WP, to better understand the workflow Leonidas, from Q-PLAN, asked for various roadmaps to understand the inputs that all the partners need to provide in relation to each activity. Leonidas asked even for a timeline in relation to the activities that are foreseen for the next months.

Moreover, he asked if it is possible to rethink / redesign the Lab in Greece. Paola said that there is a possibility to re-think the MARINEWIND Lab position (the project does not provide a specific task for the Lab, but their activities are described within various WPs and Tasks).

Regarding, T1.2 Riccardo and Arianna presented the activities foreseen within the task. They presented the guideline made to support and help the partners in the identification of stakeholders and relevant actors who work in the wind offshore field or are linked to this sector (as environmental associations, policy makers). Together with the guideline, they will share an Excel file that will be useful for developing a database for the relevant stakeholders.

All the documents will be uploaded on the MARINEWIND SharePoint.

A WP1 meeting will be organized.

WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis

Raquel from SENER showed a presentation on WP2 activities, underling how important it is to coordinate WP2, WP1 and WP3.

Social and environmental barriers analysis should be made, with a Lab focus, considering all the relevant literature.

She will ask for all the materials, from all the partners, to conduct a first national analysis.

To better conduct an on-the-ground analysis, she proposed to conduct interviews among the stakeholders that will be mapped within T1.2.

Furthermore, she proposed organizing a meeting, between January and February, to talk about the tools that the project partners will use and to see the structures on all the files and folders useful for the project activities.

A WP2 meeting will be organized too.

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey

Paola from UoY (WPL): literature on technological barriers is in working in progress but it is necessary to start a data collection and to compare the ideas to better understand the technological point of view.

Paola pointed that, as a repository platform, she will use Google Drive and, e.g., once a deliverable is ready to be uploaded on the EU platform, it will be even uploaded on the MARINEWIND SharePoint by the coordinators.

A WP3 meeting will be organized too.

WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools – WP4 was not addressed due to its durability from M6 to M36.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Ana (from WAVEC) presented the communication materials as MARINEWIND logo and the PPT template. Moreover, they are working on:

- MARINEWIND website;
- Social medias as LinkedIn and Twitter and;
- Template for the deliverables.

It has also been requested the MARINEWIND template background, to be used during the multiple events that will be held online.

APRE presented then the Excel file that will be useful for monitoring all the EU funded projects. For reasons of convenience, it has been developing only a file for mapping both the stakeholders and the

EU funded projects. The Excel file has been uploaded on the MARINEWIND SharePoint.

Lastly, regarding the exploitation activities Leonidas, from Q-PLAN, said they are working on the questionnaires that will be shared with the entire consortium to receive inputs, from the partners, on how to exploit, as best as possible, the outputs and the results of MARINEWIND.

WP6: Project Management

Riccardo presented the D6.6 – *Project Management Plan* and he focused on the Quality Plan. The latter will be as follows: the partners responsible for the design, implementation and submission are directly responsible for assuring the quality of the documents.

All deliverables produced within MARINEWIND will be reviewed and circulated following these procedures:

- Four weeks before the official EC due date, the person responsible for the deliverable must ensure that they agree with the WPL;
- Two weeks before the official EC due date, a draft version of the respective deliverable is sent to the responsible quality reviewer (Dr. Paola Zerilli, Scientific Coordinator) by the responsible project partner;
- One week before the official EC due date, the final version of the respective deliverable is sent to the PC by the responsible project partner. APRE will proceed to upload the final version to the EC after a final review.

When the responsible of the Deliverable overlaps with the WPL it will be decided *ex ante* who will make the first check among the TLs of the relative WP.

The Deliverable will be shared with all the partners to add inputs and feedbacks. It will be uploaded by the end of December.

3.3 2nd MONTHLY MEETING (January 2023)

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2023-01-10

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta; Arianna D’Addezio

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

Name	Initials	Organisation
Riccardo Coletta	RC	APRE
Arianna D’Addezio	ADA	APRE
Raquel Juan Hernandez	RJH	SENER
Leonidas Parodos	LP	Q-PLAN
Georgios Spyridopoulos	GS	Q-PLAN

Name	Initials	Organisation
Janete Goncalves	JG	WAVEC
Luca Greco	LG	CNR
Elena Ciappi	EC	CNR
Francesco Lanni	FL	RSE
Giuseppe Palazzo	GP	RSE
Laura Serri	LS	RSE
Davide Airoidi	DA	RSE
Rosalie Tukker	RT	EUROPECHE
Paola Zerilli	PZ	UoY
Connor Innes	CI	ESC
Inés Tunga	IT	ESC

MINUTES

The second monthly meeting was held on January 10, 2023, remotely (length: 1 hour). The meeting addressed the various WPs with a focus on the actions foreseen for the first semester. Below the main points addressed for each WP:

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation

Luca Greco and Elena Ciappi showed to the consortium the main template structure, in the context of T1.1, for the information collection about the authorization process of offshore wind at country (lab) level. The aim of the document is to have a common structure to support the responsible ones to carry out the research and collect similar data. The document will be even constructed for being the basis for the environmental impact analysis (WP2) and financing, techno-economic analysis (WP3).

The document has been divided into various sections, among them: legislative aspects, technical aspects and additional information. The document will be shared with all the other partners once the PC and the Scientific Coordinator have added their inputs and comments.

Moreover, APRE has recommended to the partners to start the mapping of the actors and stakeholders, in the context of T1.2.

WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis

SENER started the analysis based on the literature research. All the referral materials have been shared within the MARINEWIND SharePoint.

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey

UoY started the analysis based on the literature research – Paola made a first review of the literature and she collected the more interesting materials. All the referral materials have been shared within the MARINEWIND Google Drive (UoY for privacy reasons cannot use the SharePoint).

WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools – WP4 was not addressed due to its durability from M6 to M36.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Janete (WAVEC) said that she is working on the development of the MARINEWIND website as well as the setting up of the project social medias. She asked to all the partners to support WAVEC in finding the most suitable images for the project.

In the context of WP5, Q-PLAN asked for the inputs and feedback that each partners should give, within the T5.4, to questionnaires for the strategic exploitation plan. The latter will be useful for Q-PLAN for the development of the Deliverable 5.7 Strategic Exploitation Plan – Strategy.

WP6: Project Management

APRE said that they are working on finalizing the Advisory Board members list - they are totally on time to respect the Milestone set for the end of January.

Moreover, the PCs said they have uploaded the Deliverable 6.6 - Project Management Plan and they are working on Deliverable 6.4 Ethical issues Report that will be shared with the other partners, for feedback, by the end of the month.

3.4 3rd MONTHLY MEETING (February 2023)

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2023 – 02 - 14

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta; Arianna D'Addezio

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

	Partner	Name
1	APRE	Riccardo Coletta
1	APRE	Arianna D'Addezio
1	APRE	Flaminia Rocca
2	CNR	Elena Ciappi
2	CNR	Luca Greco
3	Q-PLAN	Leonidas Parodos
3	Q-PLAN	George Spyridopoulos
4	WAVEC	Janete Goncalves
5	SENER	Raquel Juan Hernandez
6	RSE	Laura Serri

6	RSE	Davide Airoidi
6	RSE	Giuseppe Palazzo
8	UoY	Paola Zerilli
9	CATAPULT	Connor Innes
9	CATAPULT	Inès Tunga

MINUTES

The third monthly meeting was held on February 14, 2023, remotely (length: 1.5 hour). The meeting addressed the various WPs, the changes that have been requested by the Associated Partners of the Consortium referring to the Consortium Agreement, and the possibility of application for the European Maritime Day. Below the main points addressed:

Consortium Agreement Revision

Riccardo from APRE (as PC) informed the Consortium that APRE and UoY had a call concerning the request, coming from the legal team of UoY, of making some changes in the Consortium Agreement, because it is not fully in line with their obligations as Associated Partners, as well as for other UK partners.

It is not a matter of substantial changes, but only of small one when it comes to terminology of some articles to better underline the distinction between Beneficiaries, who have obligation to the EU Commission as they signed the Grant Agreement, and the Associated Partners (in this case all coming from the UK).

The main points have already been defined. Riccardo reminded that, since the only document signed by the whole Consortium is the CA, it will be necessary a renewal of the signature by all, especially by Associated Partners, after those changes would have been made.

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation

- Davide from RSE (as WPL) explained that they are in line with the workplan, the activities of T1.1 and T1.2 have already started, and they are currently starting to think of a date for the face-to-face workshop, which is supposed to be in August but maybe will have to be anticipated or postponed. In June, the Guidelines for the co-creation activities will be created and shared.
- Riccardo from APRE suggested to finalise the actual needs the Consortium must expect from stakeholders, to start organising the labs.
- RSE asked for a deadline for each partner to complete the information concerning the database, which APRE already filled. Arianna from APRE said that by the next monthly meeting all the partners will be asked to complete the database to know exactly what stakeholders the Consortium wants to involve in the activities. Q-PLAN almost completed the Excel file of the database too. It was agreed that by the end of the month a 1st check will happen with a final check by next monthly meeting.
- Davide reminded that, since the report is due by the end of October, it has to be finished by the end of September, according to the deadlines put by APRE in the Management Plan in the section dedicated to the deliverables submission (usually 1 month before the official submission the 1st draft is due, in order to allow comments, and final review by the Project Coordinator and the Scientific Coordinator). Arianna prepared an Excel file with deliverables

and deadlines for 1st and final draft: on SharePoint it will be put in WP6 folder.

- Paola from UoY, the Scientific Coordinator, asked news to Davide from RSE for the consenting survey. Davide spoke about mid-March for the 1st draft, since in Italy the consent process is a bit difficult.
- CNR asked if the template of the survey is final, and RSE replied that it is, and the final version is on SharePoint, ready to be sent to stakeholders to be completed.
- Paola (SC) will have a meeting about WP3 and explained the absence of Ahmed for health issues.
- Leonidas from Q-PLAN said that they have not started working on the consenting process, yet.
- For the workshop, Riccardo from APRE added that, apart from thinking about practical details like place and time, an agenda must be planned.

WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis

- Raquel from SENER (as WPL) explained that they both are reviewing the papers already collected and looking for new material.
- Luca from CNR suggested it would be better to have a drop out menu on topics in the Excel file for papers and literature. Raquel suggested to group the topics. The invitation is to attain to the official list of topics.

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey

- Paola (SC) showed the progress in the Survey for stakeholders aimed at collecting data on the cost of energy/financial aspects, it is a specific questionnaire for financial evaluation, barriers and enablers, it is like the questionnaire for the partners in WP1. Financial and Commercial parts have been removed from questionnaire of WP1 and put only on the WP3 questionnaire to avoid repetitions. The basis for the content is literature on the topic. Something like the financial must be done to the technical questionnaire, and Paola asked Ines from CATAPULT to do it.
- Ahmed started to add something on the technical part and Ines put some comments on technical barriers and enablers. Paola said that it is ok, but it must be further developed, and whatever are the barriers in the other documents, it must be mirrored in the questionnaire aimed at receiving inputs from partners. Paola proposed a bilateral meeting with Ines on WP3.

WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools – WP4 was not addressed due to its durability from M6 to M36.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

- Janete from WAVEC presented a slideshow about their progress: they are finalising a Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan, whose deliverable is due for M5 (March).
- Task 5.2 Activities of C&D, M6: the website is now temporary, just missing some pictures. LinkedIn page is active, but the banner needs to have the EU logo and then we will disseminate the page. Section to upload deliverables and documents which are public has been inserted on the website. Privacy and policy cookies connected to Google Analytics will be present in the final version. Twitter account is in development.
- MARINEWIND will be at the conference in April in Copenhagen with a poster that they are developing. The poster will be shared by the end of the week to be checked by Paola (SC).

- Press release will be send out soon with the website link.
- Task 5.3 Networking: Arianna from APRE presented an Excel file where to put together stakeholders and previous projects, some partners already added some projects, she invited to continue.
- T5.4 Exploitation Plan: George from Q-PLAN explained that they received some feedback from all partners except from ELEMENT, they developed a matrix based on it where they identified project results, the key exploitable results, and framework IPR in a preliminary version to protect the results. By the end of February, it will be shared. Leonidas said that they are ahead of the schedule, their deliverable will be ready by end of February/beginning of March. Paola offered to make the exchanges with ELEMENT easier since she speaks to them for various project and explained that they have not provided feedback yet since they are still waiting for their central office to approve some aspects.
- End of March, M5, the deliverable of Strategic C&D plan is due, so by the end of February the coordinator was supposed to receive the 1st draft: Janete asked for 6/7 March, Riccardo agreed. 7 March Janete will send to the coordinator the first draft

WP6: Project Management

- Arianna from APRE asked the partners who have not uploaded the Ethics Declaration to proceed.
- Ines from CATAPULT explained that she must speak with the legal department to understand who will sign but the draft is already on SharePoint.

European Maritime Day

The application is due by Feb the 28th and it is different for each country. APRE is considering applying together with the other Italian Partners - Arianna said that it would be better to apply from all partner countries. The type of activity to be organise must be agreed upon, APRE was thinking about information activities, or something related to the education sector (offshore and renewable energies). APRE would like to submit for Italy and encouraged other partners to do it, even though it is not mandatory. Last year, APRE organised a 1-day meeting in Ravenna for another project (X-PRESS) and previewed MARINEWIND because it had been already approved.

Riccardo spoke about the possible date, maybe May/June. He also underlined, together with Paola, how meaningful in terms of visibility for the project activities to have the label of the EU maritime day. Riccardo explained that, in the application form, the participants must provide just a concept and organisation structure, but not to detail it so much yet. In a week APRE will come back to the partners for feedback on the matter, and in the meantime APRE will start to think of how to shape the event together with other Italian partners.

3.5 4th MONTHLY MEETING & CONSORTIUM GENERAL ASSEMBLY (March 2023)

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2023 – 03 – 14

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta; Arianna D’Addezio, Flaminia Rocca

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

	Partner	Name
1	APRE	Riccardo Coletta
1	APRE	Arianna D'Addezio
1	APRE	Flaminia Rocca
2	CNR	Elena Ciappi
2	CNR	Luca Greco
3	Q-PLAN	Leonidas Parodos
3	Q-PLAN	George Spyridopoulos
5	SENER	Raquel Juan Hernandez
6	RSE	Giuseppe Palazzo
6	RSE	Francesco Lanni
7	EUROPECHE	Rosalie Tukker
8	UoY	Paola Zerilli
9	CATAPULT	Connor Innes
9	CATAPULT	Mari Roberts
9	CATAPULT	Ines Tunga

Grant Agreement & Consortium Agreement Revision (Associated Partner from UK, 10 - ELE leaving the consortium)

The MARINEWIND Consortium **discussed the definitive termination of Associated Partner #10 – Element Energy (ELE)**. At least one representative of each Consortium member was present except for WAVEC. Since no representative from WAVEC was present due to a conflict of schedule, their final confirmation for the decision taken during the Assembly will be requested in written form by e-mail by the PC in the next few days.

ELE will be terminated from the consortium and being it an Associated Partner from UK, there will no budget from the European Commission to be reassigned. The solution chosen by the Consortium is to distribute ELE's efforts in PMs between the remaining two UK Associated Partners, meaning University of York and CATAPULT. The only change to be made on the Funding & Tender portal, then, will be the termination of ELE and consequently to reassign ELE PMs and tasks to UOY and CATAPULT. The two Associated Partners agreed on a bilateral meeting to finalise the distribution of the efforts. Their final distribution will be shared with the partners before being officially upload on the portal.

Leonidas from QPLAN required a further amendment: they need to change the location for their lab. The PC and the rest of the Consortium agreed. Riccardo from APRE, as PC, requested QPLAN to send information on the new location in Greece as soon as possible. The end of March was agreed as due date for sending the aforementioned information to be added as amendment to the Grant Agreement.

The PC reminded the whole Consortium that the Consortium Agreement needs to be signed, without

ELE as part of the Consortium and he reminded that three partners (UoY, RSE and ESC) should add to Annex 1 the relevant background knowledge as suggested by Leonidas.

The PC also confirmed to QPLAN that the CA will be ready before the due date of QPLAN's deliverable (that contains some references to the CA that should not be change), due for the end of April.

Paola from UoY and Riccardo from APRE confirmed that ELE is leaving the Consortium merely for a strategic corporate decision, since the board do not want to be involved in EU funded projects anymore.

The on-going WPs current situation was later briefly discussed.

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation: Giuseppe RSE informed the Consortium of the absence of news from their side, as well as from SENER's side, as Raquel confirmed (**WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis**). Inès from CATAPULT shared a new report by CCC highlighting areas specific to WP1 and WP3, also added in the excel reference she had previously uploaded on the shared MARINEWIND G-drive repository (<https://www.erm.com/news/erm-acquires-element-energy/>).

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey: Paola from UoY informed that the document concerning barriers and enablers for the topic of WP3 had been divided into two documents: one dedicated to the financial barriers and enablers and another for the socio-economic ones.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation: The PC has briefly presented the activities. In particular, he underlined how WAVEC has been completing the project website, and the Deliverable is due for the end of March (M5). WAVEC already asked, during the past few weeks, comments and suggestions from the rest of the Consortium.

WP6: Project Management: Besides changes in the GA and the CA, Riccardo from APRE informed the Consortium that the general meetings will continue online for the next 6 months.

It has been pointed out that the Project Officer already approved the first due deliverables for MARINEWIND.

Regarding the application to the European Maritime Days, Italy (APRE as applicant with support from CNR and RSE), UK (UoY and CATAPULT as joint applicants), Spain (SENER) and Greece (QPLAN) submitted it to organise their workshops in the EMD framework.

3.6 5th MONTHLY MEETING (April 2023)

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2023 – 04 - 11

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta; Arianna D'Addezio

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

1	APRE	Riccardo Coletta
1	APRE	Arianna D'Addezio
1	APRE	Flaminia Rocca
2	CNR	Elena Ciappi
2	CNR	Luca Greco
3	Q-PLAN	Leonidas Parodos
3	Q-PLAN	George Spyridopoulos
4	WAVEC	Ana Brito e Melo
5	SENER	Raquel Juan Hernandez
6	RSE	Laura Serri
6	RSE	Giuseppe Palazzo
6	RSE	Franesco Lanni
6	RSE	Davide Airoldi
7	EUROPECHE	Rosalie Tukker
8	UoY	Paola Zerilli
8	UoY	Ahmed Djeddi

MINUTES

The fifth monthly meeting was held on April 11, 2023, remotely (length: 1 hour).

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation

4 European Maritime Day Events have been approved by the European Commission (in 4 countries: Italy, UK, Greece and Spain). For Italy, Davide from RSE is in contact with Puglia Region that will come back in a few days with final location (Bari or Brindisi), then the agenda will be planned. Leonidas from QPLAN informed that the location will probably be Athens, and the time October. For UK, there will be two events, in Aberdeen and in Glasgow, in October and November, in connection with other events that Ines from CATAPULT is organising.

Raquel from SENNER said that they are considering locating the Spanish event in Catalogna, in September.

Flaminia, from APRE informed the consortium that MARINEWIND will be presented in the framework of the advocacy event "ASK4Green: an Advocacy for Social Key-instances in the Green Transition", that will happen on June, the 8th 2023 as partner event of the EU Green Week.

Elena from CNR informed that, concerning Task 1.2, all countries delivered the survey on the consenting process, in the next few weeks they will try to collect, summarise and analyse the data. The deliverable is due for the end of October.

WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis

No relevant updates have been dealt with.

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey

Concerning the support policies, the first deliverable is due for M18.

Paola from UoY showed the updates on files about the 2 main section, financial and economic evaluation and technical enablers and barriers. The simulation file will be shared when all the data are ready.

WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools – WP4 was not addressed due to its durability from M6 to M36.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Leonidas from Q-PLAN explained that the deliverable is ready, and George will make some final updates before the review by Riccardo and Paola. It is agreed to avoid including the background item that UoY and CATAPULT provided.

Ana from WAVEC agreed on sending a more finalised draft of the following monthly Press offices for the project. The consortium agreed upon having a meeting to discuss communication issues.

Arianna updated the logo “Co-funded by the European Commission” in the deliverable, a change requested by the PO.

WP6: Project Management

Concerning the change of Project Officer, APRE and UOY met her last week and informed her on the amendment. The new PO informed them that the European Commission will organise an event in Bruxelles for all the projects related to the sea, among the 21 and 22 of November: the date is not confirmed yet, but the MARINEWIND team will be invited, and MARINEWIND annual meeting will be organised in relation to this event.

Regarding the Consortium Agreement signature, EUROPECHE, CATAPULT and SENER still must sign the CA. SENER legal team proposed a change to the clause 7.1.1, and UoY is ok with it, so the final version of the CA is ready.

A virtual meeting will happen in M8/M9, close to the first financial report.

3.7 6th MONTHLY MEETING (May 2023)

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2023 – 05 - 16

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta; Arianna D’Addezio, Flaminia Rocca

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

1	APRE	Riccardo Coletta
1	APRE	Arianna D’Addezio
1	APRE	Flaminia Rocca
2	CNR	Elena Ciappi

2	CNR	Alessia Lucarelli
2	CNR	Luca Greco
3	Q-PLAN	Leonidas Parodos
3	Q-PLAN	George Spyridopoulos
4	WAVEC	Janete Goncalves
5	SENER	Raquel Juan Hernandez
6	RSE	Davide Airoldi
6	RSE	Giuseppe Palazzo
7	EUROPECHE	Rosalie Tukker
8	UoY	Paola Zerilli
8	UoY	Ahmed Djeddi
9	CATAPULT	Ines Tunga
9	CATAPULT	Connor Innes

MINUTES

The sixth monthly meeting was held on May 16th, 2023, remotely (length: 1 hour).

WP6: Project Management

Riccardo from APRE informed the Consortium that the amendments have been uploaded (termination of ELE and its task and efforts have been split between UoY and CATAPULT). Concerning the internal financial report, during next monthly meeting, APRE will explain which kind of information will be required to properly monitor the state of the art of financial reporting and if it's going in parallel with technical activities.

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation

APRE and RSE informed the consortium that they are proceeding in planning their co-creation workshop in Bari. The 1st part of the agenda will be dedicated to interventions, while the 2nd to the co-creation activity, engaging local stakeholders, fishermen, environmental, social and economic players to collect inputs for barriers and enablers.

This workshop will be used as a pilot for the guidelines that APRE will provide to the Consortium, under the Task1.3, for the other workshops, especially concerning what must be monitored and reported. During the workshop, one of the tools that could be used, to make surveys and questionnaires, it could be MENTIMETER. The co-creation approach and methodology will vary according to the number of participants. Quintuple Helix stakeholders will be reached out through

several activities during the project lifespan. The 1st of the three workshops will be mainly dedicated to the barriers perceived by the stakeholders. The other two workshops, instead, will focus mainly on potential solutions and policies to ease the installation of plants. It might be necessary to use different approaches.

WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis

Raquel from SENER informed the Consortium that, by the end of May, they will complete the document on socioeconomic barriers and then they will start completing the socioeconomic survey. Elena from CNR spoke about the EU funded project SYMBIOSIS (concerning possible conflicts of FOWTs with defense). The Consortium agreed to meet their responsible to understand if MARINEWIND results could be useful to them and vice versa.

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey

Paola from UoY informed the consortium that, for the financial part, they are testing LCOE (levelized cost of electricity), the perspective calculation code for next 20 years, simulating future behaviour of inflation rates, interests etc...and other variables.

WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools

WP4 kick off meeting happened on Friday May the 12th. QPLAN and RSE are completing the Action Plan on SharePoint. Task 4.1 started, meaning the development of WEBGIS tool, and, during the kick-off, RSE gave a presentation of the tool.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Janete from WAVEC updated about the state of the project newsletter, and said that they will promote the 1st workshop, besides the presentation of MARINEWIND methodology in APRE EU Green Week Partner Event, the Workshop “ASK 4 Green: an Advocacy for Social Key-instances in Green Transition”.

3.8 7th MONTHLY MEETING (June 2023)

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2023 – 06 - 15

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta; Arianna D’Addezio, Flaminia Rocca

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

1	APRE	Riccardo Coletta
1	APRE	Arianna D’Addezio
1	APRE	Flaminia Rocca
2	CNR	Elena Ciappi
2	CNR	Luca Greco
3	Q-PLAN	Leonidas Parodos
3	Q-PLAN	George Spyridopoulos

4	WAVEC	Ana Brito e Melo
4	WAVEC	Laura Aguilera
5	SENER	Raquel Juan Hernandez
6	RSE	Laura Serri
6	RSE	Davide Airoidi
6	RSE	Giuseppe Palazzo
6	RSE	Francesco Lanni
9	CATAPULT	Ines Tunga
9	CATAPULT	Connor Innes
9	CATAPULT	Florence Lee

MINUTES

The seventh monthly meeting was held on June 15th, 2023, remotely (length: 1 hour).

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation. Riccardo from APRE updated the consortium about the 1st workshop of the Italian Lab, held in Bari in June, the 13th 2023 under the framework of the European Maritime Days. This event acted as pilot, and APRE will soon share the guidelines for the other labs, the MENTIMETER as tool for the cocreation part, and the template for data collection. A recap of the structure of the 3 workshops per Lab has been made: the 1st of the three workshops will be mainly dedicated to the barriers perceived by the stakeholders. The other two workshops, instead, will focus mainly on potential solutions and policies to ease the installation of plants. It might be necessary to use different approaches. A brief overview will be presented also in the report.

WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis. Raquel from SENER updated the consortium about having finished the literature review; they are currently working on the survey for barriers and enablers for socio economic issues (for the environmental issue they are working with CNR). Connor from CATAPULT asked news about the European Defence Agency project that could relate to MARINEWIND activities for potential collaboration. Riccardo replied that news should be received in the next few weeks.

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey. Francesco from RSE updated the data given to Paola for her simulation, so UOY is preparing a new analysis. The calculation model is progressing. EMD gave lots of inputs for this analysis, not only about data, but also costs, barriers about the technical economic aspects. Inès from CATAPULT informed that they are working on the technological aspects, they are finalising a draft to be put on the SharePoint. She also informed that, together with UoY and RSE, they are thinking about creating a small tool for flexibility.

WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools. Leonidas from QPLAN informed that they are setting the map for T1.4, the only task running for now, and that the offline development version of the WebGis tool will be presented as draft to the consortium in July.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation. Riccardo from APRE requested WAVEC a call to discuss the opportunity to create more material to present the project, needed by the end of the summer in perspective of the next labs workshops. A media kit would be necessary as virtual package

to be printed, a media kit. An online newsletter should be added, too, as Inès reported that, after presenting MARINEWIND during APRE EU Green Week Partner Event in Brussels, called “Ask 4 Green”, she was asked by Dr. Cristiana Marchitelli from EC to receive news on the project outputs, especially regarding policies.

WP6: Project Management - Laura Aguilera joined the consortium as newest WAVEC team member. Concerning the amendments to the GA, they have been uploaded but APRE has not received any feedback yet: anyway, for now no action is requested to the consortium on that matter.

3.9 8th MONTHLY MEETING (July 2023)

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2023 – 07 - 11

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta, Flaminia Rocca

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

1	APRE	Riccardo Coletta
1	APRE	Flaminia Rocca
2	CNR	Elena Ciappi
3	Q-PLAN	Leonidas Parodos
3	Q-PLAN	George Spyridopoulos
4	WAVEC	Laura Aguilera
4	WAVEC	Janete Goncalves
5	SENER	Raquel Juan Hernandez
6	RSE	Laura Serri
6	RSE	Martina Aiello
7	EUROPECHE	Rosalie Tukker
8	UoY	Paola Zerilli
8	UoY	Ahmed Djeddi
9	CATAPULT	Ines Tunga
9	CATAPULT	Connor Innes

MINUTES

The eight monthly meeting was held on July 11th, 2023, remotely (length: 1,5 hour).

WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools. Martina from RSE showed the consortium the basic structure of the WebGIS, composed by classical elements of typical GIS (navigating guide, main page with the map and the layers). For now, administrative boundaries have been uploaded. RSE thought of adding an external webpage connected to the WebGIS, for all the data that are external from the

layers. Martina specified that the tool is made for maps and basic analysis, not data processing. A debate on whether the external page would be the best solution started, with inputs from all partners. According to RSE, this is in fact the best option because WebGIS are intended for geographic data visualisation, while other data should be inserted in a connected page, because, to avoid difficulties in navigating the page, there should be homogeneity in data formats and types. As PM, Riccardo from APRE suggested to insert basic information and then to guide the users through a link to another MARINEWIND official repository.

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation. The consortium provided updates on their respective Labs 1st workshop, as the 1st cycle has started on June, the 13th with the 1st co-creation workshop in the Italian Lab. Raquel from SENER informed that they are adapting the guidelines provided by APRE for their workshops, which will be held in late September. Concerning the UK meetings (that will be two, the former in October and the second in early November), they are reaching out to Renewable UK. Leonidas from QPLAN updated about Greek workshop, that will be held in late October, and about which they are contacting famous organisations to co-organise. For Portugal, WAVEC agreed that they are oriented towards October. The 1st cycle should be completed by M12 (October 2023).

WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis. Raquel from SENER updated the consortium about the fact that they are working on the questionnaire.

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey. Paola from UoY updated the consortium that, while the country specific questionnaire for technical barriers has been completed, the one regarding financial barriers is currently in review phase. Nevertheless, the consortium should start preparing the survey for T3.3, that will have to be filled by at least 70 people per each LAB. The 1st draft of this survey should be inspired by the country specific questionnaires for barriers, adding questionnaires from WP1. Furthermore, Paola showed the draft analysis she is making for the Italian Lab, together with RSE and CNR, with data needed to calculate the value of the investment in certain areas. This analysis will be requested for other Lab countries, too, for the second draft of the deliverable if not for the first.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation. Janete from WAVEC showed the consortium the communication materials they are preparing, to allow the Labs to show MARINEWIND brand during their workshops. The project website is currently ongoing, while the press release is to be sent out soon. Merchandising and infographic videos will be ready soon (rollup, 1st flyer version, and so on).

Concerning dissemination, Riccardo from APRE informed that CINEA invited the consortium to present MARINEWIND to the “Wind Energy projects clustering event”, due on 21st-22nd November 2023, at CINEA, Brussels.

WP6: Project Management. Riccardo from APRE asked the consortium to start thinking about who will host the annual meeting on M12. Then, a doodle will be sent to set up the date. Furthermore, he informed that the amendments received some small comments by the PO, to which the Project Coordinator and the Scientific Coordinator already replied. In conclusion, the next monthly meeting has been moved to August, the 29th.

3.10 9th MONTHLY MEETING (August 2023)

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2023 – 08 - 29

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta, Flaminia Rocca

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

1	APRE	Riccardo Coletta
1	APRE	Flaminia Rocca
2	CNR	Elena Ciappi
2	CNR	Alessia Lucarelli
2	CNR	Luca Greco
3	Q-PLAN	Leonidas Parodos
3	Q-PLAN	George Spyridopoulos
4	WAVEC	Laura Aguilera
4	WAVEC	Janete Goncalves
5	SENER	Aldara Martinez Guardado
5	SENER	Raquel Juan Hernandez
6	RSE	Francesco Lanni
8	UoY	Paola Zerilli
8	UoY	Ahmed Djeddi
9	CATAPULT	Connor Innes
9	CATAPULT	Florence Lee

MINUTES

The ninth monthly meeting was held on August 29th, 2023, remotely (length: 1 hour).

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation.

Elena from CNR explained that, together with RSE, they are preparing the draft of D1.1 - Analysis of policy and regulatory barriers and enablers: after a meeting, they decided to collect the main information in the text, and then attach the complete questionnaires from the labs as annexes. Elena asked Paola of UoY to verify with Ines from CARAPULT their comments on the UK questionnaire, to be sure about the information. Next week Paola and Ines will have a meeting on the financial part, to provide more material if needed.

Concerning the cocreation workshops, for UK, Florence and Connor from CATAPULT informed that they are proceeding organising their meeting in Aberdeen, Scotland, on October the 4th. Paola asked CATAPULT to reserve a slot for UoY to present the first financial results and requested a meeting to prepare the agenda. Leonidas from QPLAN informed the consortium that, for the Greek workshop, they are in contact with two interesting options, the former being a conference (international but focusing on the Offshore Wind in Greece) in Athens at the end of October, and a conference on Renewable Energy Sources in general at the beginning of November. Both options seemed to be fine

for the PC. About the workshop in Portugal, Laura from WAVEC informed that they are currently identifying participants and stakeholders, and that the workshop will probably be in English, and will be held at the end of October as well. Riccardo from APRE requested to know the exact dates as soon as possible. Aldara for SENER explained that they already sent a draft agenda for the Spanish workshop, and currently they are closing the contact list, including for now the expected 30 participants (as per target).

WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis. Aldara from SENER informed that they are currently working on Task 2.1 and Task 2.2, and elaborating different reference materials.

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey. Paola from UoY informed that, since D3.1 is about financial barriers, enablers and financial evaluation, they are preparing the financial evaluation for Italy and UK, as preliminary Labs, then they will extend the analysis to the other labs. Paola will have a questionnaire circulating for financial barriers, similar to questionnaire related to WP1. For D3.2, concerning the technical aspects, CATAPULT is updating the draft, that will be ready by the end of September. A meeting between Italian and UK partners will be held next week to revise the results of the preliminary analysis, in order to be able to share the deliverable draft with all the partners.

WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools. Leonidas from QPLAN informed that there are no news and T4.1, of which RSE is in charge, is running well. Concerning the following tasks, that will start in November, Riccardo from APRE asked Leonidas to let APRE know if they need a slot in the annual meeting agenda to discuss them.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation. For D5.2, due for M12, WAVEC informed that a first draft will be ready at the beginning of October. Riccardo from APRE reminded that all partners need from them at least a basic promotional package for their incoming CCWs.

WP6: Project Management.

Riccardo from APRE showed a PPT about pending incoming deliverables. He then proceeded showing the partners the template for the 1st internal financial report (M1-9), that should be filled by all beneficiaries in order to allow the PC to check the progress of the financial status of each partner, before APRE pays the second part of the first tranche of financing. The template includes tables for PM, related costs, and short descriptions of the activities, other direct costs and travels. No technical reports are now needed. The templated will be circulated by e-mail and should be filled in in a fortnight. If needed, APRE will arrange bilateral meetings to help completing the financial report. In conclusion, Riccardo reminded the partners that the annual meeting will be held in Brussels, hosted by EUROPECHE, on November the 23rd, and the agenda will be circulated in the next few days, together with the registration form. There is not any update concerning the amendments status.

3.11 10th MONTHLY MEETING (October 2023)

During the month of September, the monthly meeting was not held, since the previous meeting had been postponed to the end of August, due to the summer break and the consequent inability of many members of the consortium to participate in the previous weeks. For this reason, considering the constant updating of communications between partners within bilateral meetings and thematic meetings on the various WPs and Tasks, APRE, as Coordinator, has decided, in agreement with the consortium, to schedule the next monthly meeting directly in October.

MEETING DETAILS

Date(s): 2023 – 10 - 10

Organiser: Riccardo Coletta, Flaminia Rocca

Venue: TEAMS

ATTENDEES

1	APRE	Riccardo Coletta
1	APRE	Flaminia Rocca
2	CNR	Luca Greco
3	Q-PLAN	Leonidas Parodos
4	WAVEC	Laura Aguilera
4	WAVEC	Janete Goncalves
4	SENER	Aldara Martinez Guardado
5	SENER	Raquel Juan Hernandez
6	RSE	Davide Airoidi
6	RSE	Giuseppe Palazzo
8	UoY	Paola Zerilli
8	UoY	Ahmed Djeddi
9	CATAPULT	Ines Tunga
9	CATAPULT	Florence Lee

MINUTES

The tenth monthly meeting was held on October 10th, 2023, remotely (length: 1 hour).

WP1: Policy framework assessment and co-creation.

Inès from CATAPULT briefly summarised their 1st cocreation workshop held in Aberdeen on October the 5th, as side event in the Floating Offshore Wind Conference (the report of the workshop will be shared by the end of the current week). As audience, they reached a variety of stakeholder groups, obtaining a good representation of the sector. Aldara from SENER was physically present in Aberdeen, too, and delivered a presentation. Janete of WAVEC supported the activity for the C&D part.

Paola from UoY informed that, for UK, that they are envisioning to organise their 3rd co-creation workshop in Wales, by M20.

Riccardo from APRE asked Laura from WAVEC for updates on the Portuguese workshop, to be held on Oct 25th.

Davide from RSE updated about the status of D1.1, with contribution from CNR: Luca from CNR said that the country questionnaires still have some unresolved comments. Inès replied that they will answer to the comments on UK survey.

Raquel from SENER updated the consortium about the Spanish workshop, too.

WP2: Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis. Raquel from SENER informed that

they're finishing the literature review, while also preparing the questionnaire on stakeholders' perception of FOWTs from societal point of view, that they'll provide by next few weeks.

WP3: Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey. Paola from UoY updated the consortium about the studies they are conducting on the public and private partnerships currently present in UK. They are building their estimation of LCOE (Levelized Cost of Electricity) and finetuning the evaluation technique.

Leonidas from QPLAN asked what the baseline is for KPIs of WP3 (pre and post activities surveys).

Paola from UoY explained that, for now, she is evaluating from a financial point of view the technologies already present, since some of them are yet present but ineffective despite their potential because of the background conditions.

Inès from CATAPULT informed that, together with Corentin from CATAPULT, they are working on D3.5, also considering the hybridisation of some models.

WP4: Development of MARINEWIND Tools. Leonidas from QPLAN explained that mainly T4.1 is ongoing, the 1st online version of WebGis will be presented during MARINEWIND annual meeting in Brussels on November, the 23rd. Davide from RSE said that they already received feedback from some partners and are waiting for some more by the beginning of November. They still must decide which kind of additional tool to insert in the WebGis, and that is another topic that could be discussed during the annual meeting. T4.2 just started the current month; they're still doing analytical review on the approach and identifying a methodology.

WP5: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation. Janete from WAVEC updated the consortium about the fact that they developed some merchandising that they're sending to the partners who are having their workshops. They are currently working on the infographic video: WAVEC had a meeting with APRE for approval of first draft graphically provided by their supplier. APRE and UoY will provide feedback on the script. For the C&D&E deliverable, Janete will send the draft by the end of the week.

WP6: Project Management. Flaminia from APRE reminded the consortium of the need to fill in the registration form to the annual meeting as soon as possible, because EUROPECHE, absent to the monthly meeting, informed that they need to have the number of participants for the social dinner. The next monthly meeting will be held on November the 14th, but it will be just a brief recap of the topics and the presentations that will be discussed during the Annual Meeting the next week.

Riccardo from APRE also reminded the consortium that during the "Wind Energy projects clustering event", due on 21st-22nd November 2023 and organised by CINEA, MARINEWIND will be able to keep networking with fellow wind energy projects. Furthermore, thanks to SENER, MARINEWIND has already been put in contact with the MSCA project BLUE PATH, with which Riccardo from APRE is envisioning some synergies, to be discussed with the consortium in Brussels.

Regarding the 1st internal financial report, the second payment will be given to QPLAN, RSE and CNR that reached the 20% as per CA.

Leonidas from QPLAN requested a session on the KPIs during the annual meeting, since it will be the last physical meeting before the EC midterm review.

Riccardo from APRE also informed the consortium that the amendment is almost finalised, but still not officially approved, since this time a quite slow process is happening.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The coordination of the consortium and the management of the update flow regarding the project activities, as well as all other communications, has so far proved linear and fruitful. The members of

the consortium have been responsive to the organisational inputs of the coordinator, and have carefully managed the reporting of their activities.

Furthermore, the exchange between Project Coordinator and Scientific Coordinator has been constant and successful, allowing both to have an all-round vision of the progress of MARINEWIND activities, both from a managerial and technical-scientific point of view.